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Studies on phytochemical analysis and antimicrobial activity of *Artocarpus communis* fruit latex against selected pathogenic microorganisms

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ABSTRACT

The latex is widely used in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and food industry as in paper, textile and petroleum industries also. The present study was carried out to assess the potential antimicrobial activity of methanolic, ethanolic and chloroform extracts of fruit latex of *Artocarpus communis* against different pathogenic bacteria and fungus. All three extracts were found to show good to moderated activity against bacteria namely Gram +ve (*Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram -ve (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and fungal stains namely *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. In methanolic extract major activity was perceived on bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and among fungi *Aspergillus niger*. In ethanolic extract maximum activity perceived on bacteria *Escherichia coli* and amongst fungi *Aspergillus flavus*. In chloroform extract determined activity was observed on bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and between fungus *Candida albicans*. Maximum activity was observed on bacterial strains compared with fungal strains. In all three extracts Minimum inhibitory concentrations were in the range of 12.5-25 mg/ml. In addition, quantitative phytochemical estimations of assured active compounds like Total phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, proteins, carbohydrates, glycosides, and alkaloids were found to be in considerable quantities.

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INTRODUCTION

Artocarpus communis (jack fruit) belongs to the family Moraceae, which is widely distributed in tropical areas including India. The plant has many potential health benefits. Jack fruit is also a rubber-producing plant, as all parts of the tree contain sticky white latex¹.

Latex is an aqueous emulsion found in the vacuoles of special secretory cells known as laticifers, which contain lipids, rubbers, resins, sugars, many proteins and enzymes². Latex is the stable dispersion (emulsion) of polymer microparticles in an aqueous medium. Latexes may be natural or synthetic. Latex as found in nature is a milky fluid found in 10% of all flowering plants (angiosperms).³ It is a complex emulsion consisting of proteins, alkaloids, starches, sugars, oils, tannins, resins, and gums that coagulates on exposure to air. It is usually exuded after tissue injury. In most plants, latex is white, but some have yellow, orange, or scarlet latex. Since the 17th century, latex has been used as a term for the fluid substance in plants⁴. It serves mainly as defense against herbivorous insects⁴. The word is also used to refer to natural latex rubber particularly for non-vulcanized rubber. Such is the case in products like latex gloves, latex condoms and clothing. It can also be made synthetically by polymerizing a monomer such as styrene that has been emulsified with surfactants. The present study was carried out to evaluate the potential antimicrobial activity of methanolic, ethanolic, and chloroform extracts of fruit latex of *Artocarpus communis*. *Artocarpus communis*, commonly known as bread fruit tree because of the "bread-like texture" of its edible fruits, is an equatorial lowland species of flowering tree in the mulberry family that grows best below elevations of 650 m⁵. *A. communis* fruit latex commonly used to treat cracked-skin and dermatosis (*A. communis* in Hawai'i), In Cameroon, the fruits of *A. communis* are used as food and other parts of the plant are traditionally used to treat headache, infectious and associated diseases such as sprains, contusions, swelling⁶⁻⁷, burns, (*A. communis* in Haiti), rashes (sap of *Artocarpus* spp. in Tahiti, Tonga), stomach pain (bark of *Artocarpus* spp. diluted latex in Samoa, Solomon Islands and Tonga), diarrhea or dysentery (diluted latex or roots boiled of *Artocarpus* spp. In Borneo, Java, Pacific Islands and Samoa), diabetes (yellow leaf as tea of *Artocarpus* spp. in Trinidad West Indies) headache (leaves of *A. communis* in Bahamas, bark in Samoa and Pacific Islands), toothache (toasted flowers of *A. communis* and *A. integra* in Java and Malaya), thrush (crushed leaf buds and latex of *A. communis* on tongue in Bahamas, Trinidad and Pacific Islands), eye problems (*A. communis* leaf or petiole juice in Futuna and Samoa), ear infections (leaves juice or diluted latex in Pacific Islands), herpes infections (*A. communis* in Amboina), fever (*A. communis* leaves in Bahamas, Malaya and Samoa), enlarged spleen⁸ (*A. communis* in Java), boils, abscess, and skin infections (leaf ash, macerated root, or latex of *Artocarpus* spp. sap in Dominican Republic, Haiti, Hawai'i, Malaya Java, Samoa, Tahiti and Tonga), this includes treatments of cardiovascular diseases (yellow leaf decoction of *A. communis* in Bahamas, Haiti, Trinidad and West Indies), chest pain and vomiting from heart problems (*Artocarpus* spp. in South Pacific), Some scientific evidences of the bioactivity of *Artocarpus communis* were reported on the extract or isolated compounds⁹⁻¹⁰. However few reports are related to the antimicrobial activity of this taxon.

The objective of the present study is to screen the methanolic, ethanolic and chloroform fruit latex extracts for their phytochemicals and potential antimicrobial activity against selected pathogenic microorganisms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant latex

A. communis plants latex was collected between April 2007 to June 2007 from the surrounding area of Simhachalam, Paderu and Aruku of Visakhapatnam district, Andhra Pradesh, India. Plant was identified as by a plant Taxonomist Dr. M. Venkaiah, Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam.

Extraction of latex

A. communis plants latex were aseptically collected and subjected to drying at room temperature for 12 hrs. The dried matter (10 g) of latex was extracted by using 100ml of organic solvents (chloroform, ethanol and methanol). The suspended solutions were left to stand for 5 days, and the resulting extract was filtered and

evaporated to dryness under reduced vacuum 60°-80°C and a brown gummy residue was obtained. The obtained residue was used to determine the antimicrobial activity.¹¹

Phytochemical and Biochemical analysis

Analysis of total phenolics

The total phenolics were determined by Javanmardietal (2003)¹² method. 50µl of methanolic, Ethanolic and chloroform extracts of the fruit latex, 2.5ml diluted Folin-ciocalteau reagent and 2.0ml of 7.5% (w/v) sodium carbonate were added and incubated at 45°C for 15min. The absorbance of all samples was measured in a spectrophotometer (*Hitachi, Germany*) at 765nm and the results were expressed as mg of Gallic acid equivalents.

Estimation of total tannins

The total tannins were determined using the Folin-Ciocalteau method (1927)¹³ To 0.1ml of fruit latex in methanol, ethanol, and chloroform extracts added 6.5ml of water and 0.5ml of Folin-ciocalteau reagent and 1.5ml of 20% sodium carbonate at over night standard solution and incubated for 1hour and the absorbance of all samples were measured in a spectrophotometer at 725nm, and the results were expressed as mg of Tannic acid equivalents.

Estimation of total flavonoids

Total flavonoids content was carried by the method of Chang *et al.* (2002)¹⁴ To 0.5ml of fruit latex in methanol, ethanol, and chloroform extracts added 1.5ml of methanol, 0.1ml of 10% aluminum chloride, 0.1ml of 1M potassium acetate and 2.8ml of distilled water, it remained at room temperature for 30 min, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 415nm on U/V visible spectrophotometer. The results were expressed as mg of Quercetin equivalents.

Estimation of Alkaloids

Total alkaloid content was estimated by the method of Sreevidya and Mehrotra(2003)¹⁵. A standard solution was prepared by dissolving 5mg of boldine and fruit latex extract separately in 5ml of warm distilled water each. Five ml of boldine solution/sample extract was adjusted to pH2-2.5 (with 0.01 M HCl), and 2ml of DR was added to form an orange precipitate that was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15min. A fterward,DR was added to the supernatant to check for complete precipitation. A 2ml amount of 1% sodium sulfide was added to the residue to form a brownish black precipitate which was centrifuged at 5000rpm for 15min. Complete precipitation was checked by further adding 1% sodium sulfide. The resulting residue was dissolved in 2ml of nitric acid with warming and sonication and then made up to 10ml with distilled water. A 5ml amount of 3% thiourea was added to 1ml of the resulting solution to form a yellow bismuth complex, of which the absorbance was measured at 435 nm. All the assays were performed in triplicate. The amount of bismuth present in the boldin solution /extract was achieved from the calibration curve of bismuth nitrate. The results were expressed as boldine, considering that is a monobasic alkaloid, and therefore the complex formed with bismuth follows a 1:1 stoichiometry. plant materials containing alkaloids were determined. The method was compared with other methods. It can be used for routine analysis of commercial samples by industries dealing with herbal drugs for standardization of plant materials containing alkaloids and for alkaloid-containing pharmaceutical products.

Estimation of total Hexosamine

Total hexosamine content was carried by the method of Wagner et.al. (1979)¹⁶. 0.5ml of the fruit latex extract was made up to 1.0ml with distilled water. Standard galactose amine (in the range of 10-40 µg) was also made up to 1.0ml. Blank comprised of 1.0ml distilled water, 0.6ml of acetyl acetone reagent was added to all the tubes and heated in a boiling water bath for 30 min. After cooling, 2.0ml of Ehrlich's reagent was added and the contents were shaken well. The pink colour developed was read at 540nm against a blank using Photochem colorimeter. The results were expressed as mg of galactose amine equivalents.

Estimation of Sialic acid

Total Sialic acid was determined by the method of Warren, (1959)¹⁷. To 0.5 ml of fruit latex in methanol, ethanol, and chloroform extracts 0.25 ml of periodate was added and incubated at 37°C for 30 min. After incubation, the reaction was arrested by the addition of 0.25 ml of arsenite. The tubes were shaken well and 2.0 ml of TBA was added and the tubes were heated in a boiling water bath for 6 min. After cooling, 5.0 ml of acidified butanol was added and the butanol phase was separated after shaking well. The absorbance was read at 540 nm against a blank treated similarly using a Photochem colorimeter. Standard solutions containing 10-50 µg of n-acetyl neuraminic acid were also treated similarly.

Estimation of proteins and carbohydrates

Total protein content was estimated by Lowry (1951)¹⁸ method and total carbohydrate content was estimated by Anthrone method as per Yemm and Willis (1954)¹⁹. Total fructose was estimated by Ashwell G. (1957)²⁰ method. Other carbohydrates like starch Hedge et al. (1962)²¹ and cellulose Updegraff D M. (1969)²² were estimated by Anthrone method.

Test Organism

The selected test organisms were purchased from Microbial Type Culture Collection (MTCC) bank, Chandigarh as a freeze dried pure culture. The bacterial cultures were revived by using MTCC specified selective growth medium. The test organisms are *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 3160), *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC 430), *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 441), *Escherichia coli* (MTCC443), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 420), *Aspergillus niger* (MTCC 961), *Aspergillus flavus* (MTCC 3396), *Candida albicans* (MTCC 227), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (MTCC 170). They were separately sub-cultured and the pure culture resub-cultured on Nutrient Agar and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar media, respectively and stored at 4°C for further studies.

Inoculum preparation

Fresh microbial cultures were prepared by streaking loop full of bacterial suspension into organism specific selective media and incubated at optimal temperature in order to maintain approximately uniform growth rate of each organism. The bacterial cultures from fresh media were compared with 0.5 McFarland turbidity standards, which is equivalent to approximately 1×10^8 bacterial cell count per ml, were maintained throughout the experimentation²³.

Antimicrobial assay

The antimicrobial activities were determined by the agar well diffusion method²⁴. All the plant latex extract along with standards Ampicillin and Fluconazole was screened *in vitro* for antimicrobial activity against gram positive bacteria *S.aureus*, *B.subtilis* and *B.cereus*, gram negative bacteria *P.aeruginosa* and *E.coli* and antifungal activities against *C.albicans*, *S.cerevisiae*, *A.niger* and *A.flavus*. The different concentrations of plant latex extract (100 mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, and 25 mg/ml and 12.5mg/ml) were used for testing antimicrobial activities. The sterile nutrient agar medium and Sabouraud dextrose agar media plates, was inoculated with test organism. The inoculation has to be completed under aseptic conditions and when the medium was in molten state. The inoculated medium was transferred to sterile Petri dishes, evenly distributed and allowed to solidify. The wells (6 mm diameter) were made by punching into the agar surface with a sterile cork borer and scooping out the punched part of the agar. Into each of these wells, 0.05mL (50µg) of the fruit latex extract /reference standard/control was added by using a micropipette. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h and 28°C for 48 hrs, respectively for the bacterial and fungal cultures. The observed zones of inhibition were measured using transparent metric ruler.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Results of the phytochemical and biochemical screening and quantitative estimations showed that *A.communis* fruit latex of different solvent extracts like methanolic, ethanolic

and chloroform extracts contains phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, proteins, carbohydrates, glycosides, and alkaloids. These metabolites present in various parts are known to have varied pharmacological actions in humans and animals²⁵. Polyphenolic compounds tend to be potent free radical scavengers and their abilities to act as antioxidants mainly depends on their chemical structure, capability to donate/accept electrons, thus delocalizing the unpaired electron with in the aromatic structure and the polyphenols are broadly classified into two categories, flavonoids and phenolic acids²⁶. Polyphenol compounds are essential for the anti-oxidation process and for bioactivities in plants²⁷⁻²⁸. The total phenol, flavonoid, tannin, proteins, carbohydrates, glycosides and alkaloid content of the *A. communis* fruit latex shown in Table-1. The total phenol content is expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalents. The total phenol content of the *A. communis* fruit latex was ranged from 6.63 ± 0.25 to 6.13 ± 0.49 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACE> ACC. Similar *A. communis* fruit latex results were reported earlier in *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant²⁹. The total flavonoid content was expressed as mg of Quercetin equivalents. The total flavonoid content of the extracts *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 14.8 ± 1.17 to 13.6 ± 0.76 mg/gm. The methanol extract had higher flavonoid content than other extracts, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACC> ACE. Similar *A. communis* fruit latex results were reported earlier in *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant³⁰. The total tannin content was expressed as tannic acid equivalent per mg. The total tannin content of the extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 1.73 ± 0.17 to 1.42 ± 0.10 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACE> ACC. The methanol extracts of the *A. communis* fruit latex had higher tannin content than the ethanol and chloroform extracts. Similar results were reported in seed extracts of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant²⁹. The total Alkaloids content was expressed boldine.as equivalent per mg. The monobasic alkaloids content of the extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 10.46 ± 0.45 to 7.56 ± 0.30 mg /gm. and decreased in the following order ACM> ACE> ACC. The methanol extracts of the *A. communis* fruit latex had higher alkaloid content than the ethanol and chloroform. Similar results were reported in *Ficus thoningii* plant²⁵. The total protein content is expressed as mg of bovine serum albumin equivalents. The total protein content of the *A. communis* fruit latex was ranged from 2.95 ± 0.05 to 2.38 ± 0.07 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACC> ACE. Similar *A. communis* fruit latex results were reported earlier in latex extract of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant³¹. The total carbohydrate content was expressed as mg of Standard Glucose equivalents. The total carbohydrate content of the extracts *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 4.59 ± 0.51 to 2.78 ± 0.16 mg/gm. The chloroform extract had higher carbohydrate content than other extracts. and decreased in the following order ACC> ACM> ACE. Similar *A. communis* fruit latex results were reported earlier in latex extract of *Euphorbia splendens var. hislopii latex* plant³². The total fructose content is expressed as mg of Standard fructose equivalents. The total fructose content of the *A. communis* fruit latex was ranged from 4.43 ± 0.11 to 2.56 ± 0.39 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACC> ACE. Similar *A. communis* fruit latex results were reported earlier in *Phoenix dactylifera* plant³³. The total starch content was expressed as mg of Standard Glucose equivalents. The total starch content of the extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 5.36 ± 0.46 to 4.84 ± 0.12 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACC> ACM> ACE. The chloroform extract of the *A. communis* fruit latex had higher starch content than the ethanol and methanol extracts. Similar results were reported in seed extracts of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant³⁴. The total cellulose content was expressed as Standard cellulose equivalent per mg. The total cellulose content of the extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 4.81 ± 0.4 to 4.62 ± 0.02 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACC> ACE. The methanol extract of the *A. communis* fruit latex had higher cellulose content than the ethanol and chloroform extracts. Similar results were reported in seed extracts of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant²⁹. The total hexose amine content was expressed as mg of galactosamine equivalents. The total hexose amine content of the extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex ranged from 5.10 ± 0.45 to 3.92 ± 0.36 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACC> ACE. The methanol extract of the *A. communis* fruit latex had higher hexose amine content than the ethanol and chloroform extracts. Similar results were reported in latex extracts of *Jatropha curcas* plant³⁵. The total Sialic acid content was expressed as mg of n-acetyl neuraminic acid equivalents. The total Sialic acid content of the extracts of

A. communis fruit latex ranged from 8.64 ± 0.15 to 8.48 ± 0.08 mg /gm, and decreased in the following order ACM> ACC> ACE. The methanol extract of the *A. communis* fruit latex had higher Sialic acid content than the ethanol and chloroform extracts. Similar results were reported in latex extracts of *Jatropha curcas* plant³⁵. The antibacterial potency of *A. communis* fruit latex extract was evaluated by the presence or absence of inhibition zones and zone diameters (mm). From the results, it is evident that the Methanolic, Ethanolic, and Chloroform extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex showed a maximum inhibitory zone in a dose dependant manner (Table.2A, 2B, 2C). However, there was no significant difference between the levels of zone of inhibition at the concentration of 100mg/ml, 50mg/ml, 25mg/ml and 12.5mg/ml. The bacterial potency of *A. communis* fruit latex in ethanolic extract on Gram-positive bacteria, *S. aureus* showed a larger diameter of clearance than that of the other methanolic and chloroform extract of Gram positive bacteria used in this study. Similarly, *A. communis* fruit latex ethanolic extract showed a maximum zone of clearance in the Gram negative bacteria *E. coli* than that of other methanolic and chloroform extracts of Gram negative bacteria. Moreover, the zone of clearance achieved by *A. communis* fruit latex extracts is comparable to that of standard antibiotic. The antifungal activity of *A. communis* fruit latex methanolic, ethanolic and chloroform extracts were evaluated using agar well diffusion method, these extracts were tested against *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, *C. albicans*, *S. cerevisia* at 12.5mg/ml, 25mg/ml, 50mg/ml, and 100mg/ml. The different concentrations of *A. communis* fruit latex respectively exhibited significant activity against all the tested fungi compared with the standard drug fluconazole. Among the various solvent extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex, methanolic extract showed significant zone of inhibition against fungi where as ethanolic and chloroform extractions showed significant inhibition against *A. niger* and *S. cerevisia* (Table.3A,3B,3C). Similar results were reported in latex extracts of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* plant³⁶. Compared to our study latex extracts are more active than seed extracts on human pathogenic bacteria and fungi, However further research is needed to identify the active agents responsible for the antibacterial and antifungal activities in methanolic, ethanolic and chloroform extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex. The standard antibiotics that we took are reported to have inhibitory effects on Antimicrobial activity of *M. indica* on root extract³⁷. and antimicrobial and phytochemical analysis of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* on seed extract²⁹. Hence these fruit latex extracts might be exhibiting similar effect, further more these results is in concert with the reports on the activities of the fruit latex on against micro organisms.

There are various reports on the literature regarding characterization of medicinal plant extracts that may inhibit the above mentioned bacteria. For example the antibacterial potential of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* bark extract has been reported³⁸. Based on our results, it is concluded that fruit latex extracts have great potential as antimicrobial compounds against microorganisms and they can be used in the treatment of infectious diseases caused by resistant microorganisms. *A. communis* showed stronger activity than the other plants against all the tested bacterial strains as reported earlier in³⁹. *A. communis* can be selected for further analysis. It can be used in further research on bioactive natural products that may result in the development of new pharmaceuticals that address therapeutic needs and such screening of various natural organic compounds and identification of active agents is the need of the novel molecule and therapeutic properties at the onset of drug discovery, which shall pay off later in drug development. The significant phytochemical entrails and antimicrobial effects of *A. communis* fruit latex extracts suggest that the latex may be a useful source for the development of novel antibiotics against pathogenic bacteria and fungi. It looks that still there is a scope for scientific studies to fully pursuit its medicinal properties to support the traditional claims as well as exploring some new and promising 'leads'. The Phenolic compounds such as flavonoids, phenolic acid and tannins possess diverse biological properties such as anti-inflammatory, anti carcinogenic and anti-atherosclerotic activities. These biological properties might be due to their antioxidant activities⁴⁰.

S.No	Parameter	Methanolic	Ethanolic	Chloroform
1	protiens	2.95±0.05	2.38±0.07	2.63±0.25
2	carbohydrates	3.13±0.66	2.78±0.16	4.59±0.51

3	fructose	4.43±0.11	2.56±0.39	2.83±0.14
4	starch	4.86±0.25	4.84±0.12	5.36±0.46
5	cellulose	4.81±0.4	4.46±0.17	4.62±0.02
6	hexoseamine	5.10±0.45	3.66±0.40	3.92±0.36
7	Sialic acid	8.64±0.15	8.06±0.30	8.48±0.08
8	phenolics	7.06±0.50	6.63±0.25	6.13±0.49
9	flavanoids	14.8±1.17	13.6±0.76	13.8±1.82
10	tannins	1.73±0.17	1.73±0.13	1.42±0.10
11	Alkaloids	10.46±0.45	8.26±0.25	7.56±0.30

Table 1: Phytochemical and biochemical analysis of Methanolic, ethanolic and chloroform extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex mg/gm values.

2A

S.No	Name of Bacterial Sps	Zone of inhibition with Methanolic extract.				
		12.5 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	50 mg/ml	100 mg/ml	Antibiotic 1mg/ml
1	E.coli	ND	12.6±2.51	14±2	17.3±1.52	18.3±3.51
2	S.aureaus	12±2	15.6±1.52	19.6±2.08	23.6±2.51	23.6±2.51
3	P.aeruginosa	12.6±2.51	14.3±1.58	15±1.41	17±2	21.3±2.08
4	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	12.6±3.51	13.3±3.51	18±3	18.3±1.41	18.3±2.51
5	B.subtillis	11±2	12.3±2.51	15±3.60	24±1.41	24.3±1.52

2B

S.No	Name of Bacterial Sps	Zone of inhibition with Ethanolic extract.				
		12.5mg/ml	25 mg/ml	50 mg/ml	100 mg/ml	Antibiotic 1 mg/ml
1	E.coli	21±1.41	26.3±3.55	31.3±2.16	35.3±2.16	37±1.41
2	S.aureaus	26±1.41	27.3±2.94	30±1.41	32.3±1.50	33±2.82
3	P.aeruginosa	14±2.82	17±1.41	18.6±3.15	21±2.82	22±1.41
4	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	15±1.41	20.6±2.16	23±2.82	25.3±2.78	26±2.82
5	B.subtillis	11±1.41	13.6±2.16	14±1.41	16±1.41	18±1.41

2C

S.No	Name of Bacterial Sps	Zone of inhibition with Chloroform extract.				
		12.5 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	50 mg/ml	100 mg/ml	Antibiotic 1 mg/ml
1	E.coli	15.3±2.16	18.6±2.16	22±1.41	26±2.82	27±2.94
2	S.aureaus	11.3±2.16	13±1.41	17.3±2.16	29±1.41	30±1.41
3	P.aeruginosa	12±2.82	12.6±2.16	14±2.82	15.3±3.55	18±1.41
4	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	12.6±2.16	15±1.41	19±2.82	22.3±3.55	23±2.82
5	B.subtillis	12±1.41	13±1.41	14±2.82	16.3±3.55	19.3±2.16

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of Methanolic (2A), Ethanolic (2B) and Chloroform (3C) extracts of *A. communis* fruit latex. Zone of inhibition expressed in mm.

ND indicates Not detected

3A

S.No	Name of Fungi	Zone of inhibition with Methanolic extract				
		12.5mg/ml	25mg/ml	50mg/ml	100mg/ml	Antibiotic 1mg/ml
1	A.niger	ND	12.6±2.51	18.3±2.51	22.6±3.05	17.6±1.56
2	A.flavus	ND	12±2	14.6±2.51	18±3	23±1
3	C.albicans	ND	15±2	17.6±3.34	19.3±2.51	22±3
4	S.cervisiae	11.6±3.34	14±2	17.3±2.08	19.3±3.51	20.6±2.08

3B

S.No	Name of Fungi	Zone of inhibition with Ethanolic extract				
		12.5mg/ml	25mg/ml	50mg/ml	100mg/ml	Antibiotic 1mg/ml
1	A.niger	10.3±1.52	11.33±1.52	13.0±2	13.6±1.52	18.0±1.0
2	A.flavus	ND	10.3±1.528	12.6±1.52	15.0±1.0	16.3±1.52
3	C.albicans	10±1	12±1	13.3±1.31	14.3±1.52	17.3±1.52
4	S.cervisiae	10±1.41	12±1.41	13.3±1.86	14.3±2.16	15.3±2.16

3C

S.No	Name of Fungi	Zone of inhibition with Chloroform extract				
		12.5mg/ml	25mg/ml	50mg/ml	100mg/ml	Antibiotic 1mg/ml
1	A.niger	ND	10 ±1	11±1	13±1	13±1.0
2	A.flavus	ND	10±1	12.6±1.52	13±1	15.3±1.52
3	C.albicans	10.3±1.52	13±2	13.6±1.52	15±2	17±2
4	S.cervisiae	10.3±2.16	13±2.82	13.6±2.16	15±1.41	15±2.82

Table 3: Antifungal activity of different extracts Ethanolic (3A), methanolic (3B) and chloroform (3C) of fruit latex of *Artocarpus communis*. Zone of inhibition expressed in mm.

ND indicates Not detected

Conclusion

Our work concludes that the Ethanolic, Methanolic and Chloroform extracts of *A.communis* fruit latex are rich in flavonoids and alkaloids respectively and when checked for anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties these extracts have shown fairly well and significant anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties in comparison with standard anti-bacterial and anti-fungal drugs. This work paves a way to develop a therapeutic strategy from natural resources, against various bacterial and fungal infections.

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